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A review of the tribe Teledapini Pascoe, 1871, with descriptions of new species from China and notes on the tribe Xylosteini Reitter, 1913 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lepturinae)

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Abstract. A review of the tribe Teledapini Pascoe, 1871, including the genera *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871, *Teledapalpus* Miroshnikov, 2000 and *Parateledapus* Miroshnikov, 2000, is provided. The morphological differences between the very similar and taxonomically complex genera *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*, which include some transitional forms, are discussed. The particularities of the distribution area of these genera are assessed. The following new species from China are described: *Teledapalpus lobanovi* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.** (Sichuan), *Teledapalpus daliensis* **sp. n.** (Yunnan) and *Teledapalpus transitivus* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.** (Yunnan). The following new combinations are established (all from *Teledapus*): *Teledapalpus aranea* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *Teledapalpus picatus* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *Teledapalpus pilosellus* (Holzschuh, 2007), **comb. n.**, and *Teledapalpus linyejiei* (Huang, Li et Zhang, 2021), **comb. n.** The keys to species of *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus* are given. The morphological differences between the tribes Teledapini and Xylosteini Reitter, 1913 are presented. The composition of the latter tribe and the systematic position of some genera characterized by coarsely faceted eyes are discussed. Abundant pictures of the taxa studied, including all holotypes and other type specimens, are provided.

Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Teledapini, Xylosteini, review, new species, new records.

Обзор жуков-дровосеков трибы Teledapini Pascoe, 1871 с описанием новых видов из Китая и заметками о трибе Xylosteini Reitter, 1913 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae: Lepturinae)

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Резюме. Представлен обзор трибы Teledapini Pascoe, 1871, включающей роды *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871, *Teledapalpus* Miroshnikov, 2000 и *Parateledapus* Miroshnikov, 2000. Обсуждаются морфологические различия между очень сходными и таксономически сложными родами *Teledapus* и *Teledapalpus*, содержащими некоторые переходные формы. Проанализированы особенности ареалов этих родов. Описаны следующие новые виды из Китая: *Teledapalpus lobanovi* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.** (Сычуань), *Teledapalpus daliensis* **sp. n.** (Юньнань) и *Teledapalpus transitivus* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.** (Юньнань). Установлены следующие новые комбинации (все из рода *Teledapus*): *Teledapalpus aranea* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *Teledapalpus picatus* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *Teledapalpus pilosellus* (Holzschuh, 2007), **comb. n.** и *Teledapalpus linyejiei* (Huang, Li et Zhang, 2021), **comb. n.** Даны определительные таблицы видов *Teledapus* и *Teledapalpus*. Приведены морфологические различия между трибами Teledapini и Xylosteini Reitter, 1913. Обсуждаются состав последней трибы и систематическое положение некоторых родов, характеризующихся крупно фасетированными глазами. Представлено большое количество иллюстраций исследуемых таксонов, в том числе всех голотипов и других типовых экземпляров.

Ключевые слова: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Teledapini, Xylosteini, обзор, новые виды, новые находки.

Introduction

Tribe Teledapini Pascoe, 1871 was established (as “subfam. Teledapinæ”) for the sole genus *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871 [Pascoe, 1871]. However, soon after this genus was moved in the tribe Cerambycini [Gemminger, 1872], and thereby placed next to taxa, now attributed to completely different taxonomic groups.

Later, *Teledapus* was transferred to the subfamily Lepturinae Latreille, 1802 or the tribe Lepturini Latreille, 1802 [Gahan, 1906; Aurivillius, 1912] and this approach was subsequently followed by other authors [Winkler, 1929], although individual researchers treated *Teledapus* as the member of Rhagiini Kirby, 1837 [Boppe, 1921].

In some contemporary works *Teledapus* is listed in Xylosteini Reitter, 1913 [Miroshnikov, 2000; Catalogue..., 2010]. At the same time, the tribe Teledapini has been restored for this genus [Bousquet et al., 2009], which is supported by the several subsequent publications [Bouchard et al., 2011; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017; Chen et al., 2019; Catalogue..., 2020].

The review of the tribe Teledapini and discussion of its differential features from Xylosteini are proposed in the present paper for the first time. In addition, the opinion is expressed on the systematic position of some Lepturinae genera characterized by coarsely faceted eyes.

The material treated in this work belongs to the following institutional and private collections:

Fig. 1. Type locality of *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n., China, Sichuan Province, Maoxian County, SE Shangxinzheng Village, 31°34'32"N / 103°47'33"E, 2935 m a.s.l. (photograph by Igor A. Belousov and Genrik E. Davidian).

Рис. 1. Типовое местонахождение *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n. (фотография И.А. Белоусова и Г.Э. Давидьяна).

BMNH – Natural History Museum (London, United Kingdom);

LPSNU – School of Biological Science and Technology, Liupanshui Normal University (Liupanshui, China);

SMNS – Staatliches Museum für Naturkunde Stuttgart (Germany);

ZMMU – Zoological Museum of the Moscow State University (Moscow, Russia);

cAM – collection of Alexandr Miroshnikov (Krasnodar, Russia);

cCH – collection of Carolus Holzschuh (Villach, Austria);

cLD – collection of Luboš Dembický (Brno, Czech Republic);

cSM – collection of Sergey Murzin (Moscow, Russia).

Tribe Teledapini Pascoe, 1871

Teledapinae Pascoe, 1871: 268.

Teledapini: Bousquet et al., 2009: 23; Bouchard et al., 2011: 463; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017: 171–172; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Type genus *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871.

Diagnosis. This tribe is most similar to Xylosteini, but differs in the features presented in Table 1.

Composition. The tribe includes the following three genera: *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871, *Teledapalpus* Miroshnikov, 2000 and *Parateledapus* Miroshnikov, 2000.

Distribution (Fig. 80). The southeast of the Palaearctic realm (Himalayas in Pakistan, India, probably in Nepal and Bhutan; China) and adjacent areas of the Oriental realm (Northern Indochina).

Genus *Teledapus* Pascoe, 1871

Teledapus Pascoe, 1871: 268; Gemminger, 1872: 2786; Gahan, 1906: 77; Aurivillius, 1912: 177; Boppe, 1921: 31; Winkler,

1929: 1148; Miroshnikov, 2000: 40; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Švácha, Lawrence, 2014: 156; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017: 172; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258; Chen et al., 2019: 87; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Type species *Teledapus dorcadioides* Pascoe, 1871.

Diagnosis. This genus is very similar to *Teledapalpus* Miroshnikov, 2000, but differs by the features presented in Table 2.

Composition. The genus includes the following four species: *Teledapus dorcadioides* Pascoe, 1871, *T. querceti* Holzschuh, 2007, *T. ocularis* Holzschuh, 1981, and *T. celsicola* Holzschuh, 1999.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Himalayas (Pakistan, India, very likely also Nepal and Bhutan); Sino-Tibetan Mountains (Hengduan Mountains) (China).

Teledapus dorcadioides Pascoe, 1871

(Figs 2–5, 31, 32, 38, 63, 69, 80, 81, 88, 89)

Teledapus dorcadioides Pascoe, 1871: 269, pl. 13, fig. 1 (type locality: “Himalaya (Mussooree)” (according to the original description); “India”, “Mussooree” (according to the labels of the holotype)); Gemminger, 1872: 2786; Gahan, 1906: 77; Aurivillius, 1912: 177; Boppe, 1921: 31, pl. 2, fig. 8; Winkler, 1929: 1148; Beeson, 1941: 211; Duffy, 1968: 66–67, fig. 26 (larva); Miroshnikov, 2000: 49, 51, 52, figs 38, 43, 44, 47; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (BMNH) (Fig. 2), “India”, “*Teledapus dorcadioides* [illegible further on]”, “Type”, “Pascoe Coll. 93–60”, “*Teledapus dorcadioides* Pasc. Mussooree” (Fig. 3); 1♂ (ZMMU) (Fig. 4), “India bor. Simla”, “*Teledapus dorcadioides* Psc. N. Plavilstshikov det.”; 1♀ (ZMMU) (Fig. 5), “Deoban, Jaunsar, VII.1920” (upperside), “W. Himalayas” (underside), “*Teledapus dorcadioides* Pasc., J.C.M. Gardner det.”

Morphological notes. Body length 14–20 mm, thereby holotype largest.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Northern India (Himalayas): Himachal Pradesh (Shimla, = Simla), Uttarakhand (Mussoorie; Deoban, Jaunsar; Chakrata).

Table 1. Distinguishing features of the tribes Xylosteini and Teledapini.
Таблица 1. Отличительные особенности триб Xylosteini и Teledapini.

Xylosteini	Teledapini
<p>Humeri straight or partly raised (humpy), as in Figs 85–87, 99–102, sometimes barely sloping outwards, thereby base of elytra approximately at level of scutellum apex always much or very distinctly wider (but not less than 1.6 times) than base of pronotum /</p> <p>Плечи прямые или отчасти приподнятые (бугристые), как на рисунках 85–87, 99–102, иногда едва скошенные к наружной части, причем основание надкрылий примерно на уровне вершины щитка всегда гораздо или значительно шире (но не менее чем в 1.6 раза) основания переднеспинки</p>	<p>Humeri sloping or sloping rounded, as in Figs 2, 4–18, 20–30, 81–84, if sometimes they look straight in a small part, as in Fig. 19, then base of elytra approximately at level of scutellum apex not more than 1.4 times as wide as the base of pronotum /</p> <p>Плечи покатые или покато-округлые, как на рисунках 2, 4–18, 20–30, 81–84, если иногда выглядят в небольшой части прямыми, как на рисунке 19, то основание надкрылий примерно на уровне вершины щитка не более чем в 1.4 раза шире основания переднеспинки</p>
<p>Males always, females with exception of <i>Xylosteus</i> with normally developed wings, thereby rudimentary wings of latters with well-expressed venation, while length of elytron 1.75–3.2 times as long as length of wing, as in Figs 85–87 /</p> <p>Самцы всегда, а самки за исключением <i>Xylosteus</i> с нормально развитыми крыльями, причем рудиментарные крылья последних с хорошо выраженным жилкованием, а длина надкрылья превышает длину крыла в 1.75–3.2 раза, как на рисунках 85–87</p>	<p>Males and females with rudimentary wings, devoid of distinct venation, while length of elytron 4.5–7.5 or more than 8 times as long as length of wing in males and females, respectively, as in Figs 78, 79, 81–84 /</p> <p>Самцы и самки с рудиментарными крыльями, лишенными отчетливого жилкования, а длина надкрылья превышает длину крыла в 4.5–7.5 или более чем в 8 раз у самцов и самок соответственно, как на рисунках 78, 79, 81–84</p>
<p>Metasternum very well-developed, much longer than mesosternum, as in Figs 96–98; if metasternum to a varying degree shortened (females of <i>Xylosteus</i> and <i>Niisatoa</i>), then even in this case it very distinctly longer (not less than 1.6 times) than mesosternum, as in Figs 92–95, while shortest distance between middle and posterior coxal cavities about 1.25–1.5 times as long as longitudinal diameter of metacoxae /</p> <p>Заднегрудь очень хорошо развита, намного длиннее среднегрудь, как на рисунках 96–98; если заднегрудь в той или иной степени укорочена (самки <i>Xylosteus</i> и <i>Niisatoa</i>), то даже в этом случае она значительно длиннее (но не менее чем в 1.6 раза) среднегрудь (рис. 92–95), а минимальное расстояние между средними и задними тазиковыми впадинами в 1.25–1.5 раза длиннее продольного диаметра средних тазиков</p>	<p>Metasternum short, not or only slightly longer (but not more than 1.2 times) than mesosternum, as in Figs 88–91, while shortest distance between the middle and posterior coxal cavities being either subequal to or shorter than longitudinal diameter of metacoxae /</p> <p>Заднегрудь короткая, не длиннее или слегка длиннее (но не более чем в 1.2 раза) среднегрудь, как на рисунках 88–91, а минимальное расстояние между средними и задними тазиковыми впадинами примерно равно продольному диаметру средних тазиков или короче его</p>
<p>Coxae clearly smaller, moderately developed, this being especially evident in pro- and mesocoxae, as in Figs 92–95 /</p> <p>Тазики явно менее крупные, умеренно развиты, что особенно заметно по передним и средним тазикам, как на рисунках 92–95</p>	<p>Coxae clearly larger, quite strong, this being especially evident in pro- and mesocoxae, as in Figs 88–91 /</p> <p>Тазики явно более крупные, довольно мощные, что особенно заметно по передним и средним тазикам, как на рисунках 88–91</p>
<p>Lateral tubercles of pronotum always well- or very strongly developed, pointed apically or strongly narrowed towards apex, at least in the form of a narrower cone /</p> <p>Боковые бугры переднеспинки всегда хорошо или очень сильно развиты, заостренные апикально или сильно суженные к вершине, по крайней мере в форме более узкого конуса</p>	<p>Lateral tubercles of pronotum from weakly developed to well-expressed, to a varying degree rounded or obtuse laterally, not acuminate, as a rule, sometimes narrowed towards apex in the form of a wider cone /</p> <p>Боковые бугры переднеспинки от слабо развитых до сильно выраженных, но, как правило, так или иначе округлые или тупые на вершине, не заостренные, иногда сужены к вершине в форме более широкого конуса</p>
<p>Elytra in males subparallel-sided, as in Figs 99–101, or narrowed to a varying degree towards apex, in females, in the vast majority of cases, subparallel-sided, as in Figs 98, 102, only in females of <i>Xylosteus</i> (Figs 85–87) and <i>Niisatoa</i> they anyway onlong-ovate (male of <i>Niisatoa</i> most probably will prove to show the shape of elytra typical of Xylosteini); in addition, elytra in the vast majority of cases with a pattern of integument, only in some <i>Notorhabdium</i> without any pattern /</p> <p>Надкрылья у самцов примерно параллельносторонние или в той или иной степени сужены к вершине, у самок в абсолютном большинстве случаев примерно параллельносторонние, как на рисунках 98, 102, лишь у самок <i>Xylosteus</i> (рис. 85–87) и <i>Niisatoa</i> так или иначе удлинненно-яйцевидные (у самца <i>Niisatoa</i> с большой вероятностью следует ожидать характерную для самцов Xylosteini форму надкрылий); кроме того, надкрылья в абсолютном большинстве случаев с рисунком интегумента, лишь у некоторых <i>Notorhabdium</i> без рисунка</p>	<p>Elytra of male in the vast majority of cases, in females, as a rule, anyway oblong-ovate, as in Figs 2, 4–9, 11–27, 29; elytra entirely monochrome, without a pattern of integument, as a rule, only sometimes with a pattern /</p> <p>Надкрылья у самцов в большинстве случаев, у самок, как правило, так или иначе удлинненно-овальные, как на рисунках 2, 4–9, 11–27, 29; надкрылья целиком однотонные, как правило, без рисунка интегумента, только иногда с рисунком</p>

Figs 2–8. Species of *Teledapus*, habitus, dorsal view, and labels.

2–5 – *T. dorcadioides*; 6–8 – *T. querceti* (photographs by Luboš Dembičský). 2–3, 6 – holotypes; 7–8 – paratypes; 2, 4, 6–7 – males; 5, 8 – females.

Рис. 2–8. Виды рода *Teledapus*, общий вид сверху и этикетки.

2–5 – *T. dorcadioides*; 6–8 – *T. querceti* (фотографии Л. Дембицкого). 2–3, 6 – голотипы; 7–8 – паратипы; 2, 4, 6–7 – самцы; 5, 8 – самки.

Table 2. Distinguishing features of the genera *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*.
Таблица 2. Отличительные особенности родов *Teledapus* и *Teledapalpus*.

<i>Teledapus</i>	<i>Teledapalpus</i>
<p>Maxillary and labial palps constantly comparatively shorter, as in Figs 31–43, 63, 69, 70 (male palps usually longer than those of females), thereby head width across temples immediately behind eyes 1.3–1.4 or 1.5–1.75 times as great as length of maxillary palpus, in males and females, respectively; second and terminal maxillary palpomeres less elongated /</p> <p>Максиллярные и лабиальные щупики сравнительно короче, как на рисунках 31–43, 63, 69, 70 (у самца щупики обычно длиннее, чем у самки), при этом ширина головы на уровне висков непосредственно позади глаз в 1.3–1.4 или 1.5–1.75 раза больше длины максиллярного щупика у самцов и самок соответственно; второй и последний членики максиллярных щупиков менее вытянутые</p>	<p>Maxillary and labial palps, as a rule, comparatively longer to much longer, as in Figs 44–58, 64–68, 71–74 (male palps usually longer than those of females), thereby head width across temples immediately behind eyes 0.7–1.1 or 0.98–1.25 times as great as length of maxillary palpus, in males and females, respectively; second and terminal maxillary palpomeres often more elongated /</p> <p>Максиллярные и лабиальные щупики, как правило, сравнительно длиннее или намного длиннее, как на рисунках 44–58, 64–68, 71–74 (у самца щупики обычно длиннее, чем у самки), при этом ширина головы на уровне висков непосредственно позади глаз в 0.7–1.1 или 0.98–1.25 раза больше длины максиллярного щупика у самцов и самок соответственно; второй и последний членики максиллярных щупиков часто более вытянутые</p>
<p>Eyes less strongly developed (in male greater than in female), occupying distinctly smaller head area, as in Figs 31–43 (in <i>T. ocellaris</i>, eyes only strongly protruding laterally, especially so in male, as in Figs 33, 39) /</p> <p>Глаза менее развитые (у самца глаза более крупные, чем у самки), занимающие отчетливо меньшую площадь на голове, как на рисунках 31–43 (глаза <i>T. ocellaris</i> лишь сильно торчащие в стороны, особенно у самца, как на рисунках 33, 39)</p>	<p>Eyes more strongly developed (in male greater than in female), occupying distinctly larger head area, as in Figs 44–59, 61 /</p> <p>Глаза более развитые (у самца глаза более крупные, чем у самки), занимающие отчетливо большую площадь на голове, как на рисунках 44–59, 61</p>
<p>Neck comparatively stronger concealed by pronotum, as in Figs 31–43 /</p> <p>Шея сравнительно сильнее скрыта переднеспинкой, как на рисунках 31–43</p>	<p>Neck comparatively less strongly concealed by pronotum, as a rule, as in Figs 44–58 /</p> <p>Шея, как правило, сравнительно менее сильно скрыта переднеспинкой, как на рисунках 44–58</p>
<p>Female body generally more robust, as in Figs 5, 8, 9, 11, 13, 14, forebody more massive, pronotum comparatively wider in most of the cases, at least so at anterior and posterior margins, as in Figs 39–43 /</p> <p>Тело самок в целом более крепкое, как на рисунках 5, 8, 9, 11, 13, 14, а голова и переднеспинка вместе выглядят более массивными, переднеспинка в абсолютном большинстве случаев сравнительно более широкая, по крайней мере в основании и на вершине, как на рисунках 39–43</p>	<p>Female body generally slenderer, as in Figs 23, 25–27, 29, forebody less massive, pronotum comparatively narrower, at least so at anterior and posterior margins, as in Figs 54–58, 61 /</p> <p>Тело самок в целом более стройное, как на рисунке 23, 25–27, 29, а голова и переднеспинка вместе выглядят менее массивными, переднеспинка сравнительно более узкая, по крайней мере в основании и на вершине, как на рисунках 54–58, 61</p>
<p>Lateral tubercles of pronotum weakly or moderately developed, as in Figs 31–43 /</p> <p>Боковые бугры переднеспинки слабо или умеренно развиты, как на рисунках 31–43</p>	<p>Lateral tubercles of pronotum generally more or less strongly developed, as in Figs 44–46, 48–56, 58; sometimes weakly or moderately developed, as in Figs 47, 57, 59, 61 /</p> <p>Боковые бугры переднеспинки в большинстве случаев более или менее сильно развиты, как на рисунках 44–46, 48–56, 58; иногда слабо или умеренно развиты, как на рисунках 47, 57, 59, 61</p>
<p>Male third antennomere moderately elongated (in female less elongated than in male), distinctly longer than basal antennomere, or comparatively weakly elongated, subequal to basal antennomere; at least antennomeres 2–5 in the vast majority of cases more thickened /</p> <p>3-й членик усиков самца умеренно вытянутый (у самки менее вытянутый, чем у самца), отчетливо длиннее 1-го членика усиков, или сравнительно слабо вытянутый, примерно равен первому членику усиков; по крайней мере 2–5-й членики усиков в большинстве случаев более утолщенные</p>	<p>Male third antennomere more or less strongly elongated (in female less elongated than in male), very distinctly longer than basal antennomere, or moderately elongated, but distinctly longer than basal antennomere; at least antennomeres 2–5 slenderer /</p> <p>3-й членик усиков самца более или менее сильно вытянутый (у самки менее вытянутый, чем у самца), очень явно длиннее 1-го членика усиков, или умеренно вытянутый, но отчетливо длиннее 1-го членика усиков; по крайней мере 2–5-й членики усиков более стройные</p>
<p>Dorsal pronotal constrictions less strongly developed at apex and base /</p> <p>Переднеспинка с менее резкими перетяжками у вершины и основания сверху</p>	<p>Dorsal pronotal constrictions in the vast majority of cases more strongly developed at apex and base /</p> <p>Переднеспинка в большинстве случаев с более резкими перетяжками у вершины и основания сверху</p>

According to Duffy [1968], this species also inhabits the Punjab and Jammu and Kashmir, which at least for the latter state is obviously true.

Teledapus querceti Holzschuh, 2007
(Figs 6–8, 9, 34, 35, 40, 43, 70, 80)

Teledapus querceti Holzschuh, 2007: 180, Abb. 3 (type locality: “North India, Uttarpradesh, Mandoli – Lohajang, 2600 m” (according to the original description)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 6); 1♂, paratype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 7); 1♀, paratype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 8); 1♀ (cLD) (Fig. 9), “N India, Uttarpradesh, Wan, 2800 m, 16.07.2003, leg. E. Kučera”.

Morphological notes. Body length 11.8–16.6 mm.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Northern India (Himalayas): Uttarakhand.

Remarks. Mundoli (= Mandoli) Village (30°08'N / 79°36'E) and Wan Village (30°12'N / 79°37'E) are now located in the State of Uttarakhand (formerly known as Uttaranchal), which was carved out from the State of Uttar Pradesh in 2000.

Teledapus ocularis Holzschuh, 1981
(Figs 10, 11, 33, 39, 80)

Teledapus ocularis Holzschuh, 1981: 94, 109 (Abb. 4–5) (type locality: Pakistan, Hazara, Kaghan Valley, Kaghan, 3000 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)); Miroshnikov, 2000: 51–52, figs 46, 49; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (Fig. 10), Pakistan, Hazara, Kaghan Valley, Kaghan, 3000 m, 13.05.1978 (leg. C. Holzschuh); 1♀, paratype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 11), Pakistan, Sari bei Shogran, 2750–2900 m, 28.06.1979 (leg. W. Wittmer).

Morphological notes. Body length 15.3 or 16.1–19.9 mm in male and female, respectively.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Northern Pakistan (Himalayas).

Teledapus celsicola Holzschuh, 1999
(Figs 12–14, 36, 37, 41, 42, 80)

Teledapus celsicola Holzschuh, 1999: 5, 53 (Abb. 1) (type locality: China, “SE Tibet “Chola Shan” pass, road Yanjing – Markam, 50 km S Markam, 29°16'N, 98°38'E, 4400 m” (according to the original description)); Miroshnikov, 2000: 51–52 figs 45, 48; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 12), “SE Tibet “Chola Shan” pass, road Yanjing – Markam, 50 km S Markam, 29°16'N, 98°38'E, 4400 m, mixed forest, 24-27.06.1997”; 1♂, paratype (cCH), same label; 1♀, paratype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 13), same label; 1♀, paratype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 14), same label.

Morphological notes. Body length 11.6–17.8 mm.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China: Tibet Autonomous Region (Sino-Tibetan Mountains).

Key to species of the genus *Teledapus*

1. Eyes moderately protruding, as in Figs 31, 32, 34–38, 40–42; antennae shorter, in male one way or another shorter than body, in female, at most, approximately reaching the middle of elytra, as in Figs 4–9 (India or China) 2
- Eyes strongly protruding, as in Figs 33, 39; antennae longer, in male slightly longer than body, in female

- distinctly reaching beyond the middle of elytra, as in Figs 10, 11 (Pakistan) *T. ocularis*
2. Tarsomeres 1 and 2 of all tarsi more elongated, as in Figs 4–9; elytra of female generally wider, more sharply widened, at least so towards the middle, starting from base, as in Figs 5, 8, 9 (India, Western Himalayas) 3
- Tarsomeres 1 and 2 of all tarsi less elongated, as in Figs 12–14; elytra of female generally narrower, less sharply widened, at least so towards the middle, starting from base, as in Figs 13, 14 (China, Hengduanshan) *T. celsicola*
3. At least antennomeres 1, 3–5 comparatively more elongated, as in Figs 2, 4, 5 *T. dorcadioides*
- At least antennomeres 1, 3–5 comparatively less elongated, as in Figs 6–9 *T. querceti*

Genus *Teledapalpus* Miroshnikov, 2000

Teledapalpus Miroshnikov, 2000: 38; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017: 172; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Type species *Teledapalpus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2000, by original designation.

Diagnosis. This genus is very similar to *Teledapus*, but differs by the features presented in Table 2.

Composition. The genus includes 13 species, three of which are described in this paper as new, while one not yet described species (Ohbayashi, Chou, in press) is mentioned here preliminarily. Amongst these are the following: *Teledapalpus murzini* Miroshnikov, 2000, *T. zamotajlovi* Miroshnikov, 2000, *T. hospes* (Holzschuh, 1999), *T. picatus* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *Teledapalpus* sp. (Ohbayashi, Chou, in press), *T. aranea* (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**, *T. zolotichini* Miroshnikov, 2000, *T. cremarius* (Holzschuh, 1999), *T. lobanovi* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**, *T. pilosellus* (Holzschuh, 2007), **comb. n.**, *T. daliensis* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**, *T. transitivus* Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**, and *T. linyejiei* (Huang, Li et Zhang, 2021), **comb. n.**

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Gansu, Shaanxi, Sichuan, Yunnan, probably Tibet); Northern Vietnam, apparently the northern areas of Laos, Myanmar and Thailand.

Teledapalpus murzini Miroshnikov, 2000
(Figs 15, 44, 80)

Teledapalpus murzini Miroshnikov, 2000: 41, 47, fig. 31 (type locality: China, N Sichuan, Nanping env., 3500 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cSM) (Fig. 15), China, N Sichuan, Nanping env., 3500 m, 10–19.06.1997, pitfall trap (leg. S. Murzin).

Morphological notes. Body length 12.9 mm.

Remarks. Until now, this species is known only from the holotype.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Sichuan).

Teledapalpus zamotajlovi Miroshnikov, 2000
(Figs 16, 45, 80)

Teledapalpus zamotajlovi Miroshnikov, 2000: 41, 47, 50 figs 32, 40 (type locality: China, N Sichuan, Juizhaigou,

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Figs 9–14. Species of *Teledapus*, habitus, dorsal view.

9 – *T. querceti*, female; 10–11 – *T. ocularis*; 12–14 – *T. celsicola*. 10, 12 – holotypes, males; 11, 13–14 – paratypes, females. Photographs by Luboš Dembický.

Рис. 9–14. Виды рода *Teledapus*, общий вид сверху.

9 – *T. querceti*, самка; 10–11 – *T. ocularis*; 12–14 – *T. celsicola*. 10, 12 – голотипы, самцы; 11, 13–14 – паратипы, самки. Фотографии Л. Дембицкого.

Figs 15–20. Species of *Teledalpus*, males, habitus, dorsal view.
 15 – *T. murzini*; 16 – *T. zamotajlovi*; 17–18 – *T. hospes*; 19 – *T. aranea* comb. n.; 20 – *T. picatus* comb. n. 15–17, 19 – holotypes (17, 19 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 15–20. Виды рода *Teledalpus*, самцы, общий вид сверху.
 15 – *T. murzini*; 16 – *T. zamotajlovi*; 17–18 – *T. hospes*; 19 – *T. aranea* comb. n.; 20 – *T. picatus* comb. n. 15–17, 19 – голотипы (17, 19 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

4000 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cSM) (Fig. 16), China, N Sichuan, Juizhaigou, 4000 m, 21–23.06.1997, pitfall trap (leg. S. Murzin).

Morphological notes. Body length 14 mm.

Remarks. Until now, this species is known only from the holotype.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Sichuan).

Teledapalpus hospes (Holzschuh, 1999)
(Figs 17, 18, 25, 46, 54, 71, 80, 84)

Teledapalpus hospes Holzschuh, 1999: 6, 53 (Abb. 2) (type locality: China, Gansu, 70 km W of Wudu, 1800–2500 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)).

Teledapalpus hospes: Miroshnikov, 2000: 43, 48–49, figs 34, 37; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (Fig. 17), China, Gansu, 70 km W of Wudu, 1800–2500 m, 7–16.06.1997 (leg. A. Shamaev); 1♂ (collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow, Russia) (Fig. 18), same label; 1♀ (cAM) (Fig. 25), same label.

Morphological notes. Body length 12.8–14.2 or 15 mm in male and female, respectively, thereby the holotype smallest.

Female (Fig. 25) closely resembles a male, but head smaller, eyes less strongly developed; antennae shorter, slightly reaching beyond the middle of elytra, most of antennomeres less elongated; terminal maxillary and labial palpomeres slenderer, not axe-shaped, as in Fig. 71; elytra wider, as in Fig. 25; legs shorter, tarsomeres 1 and 2 less elongated; in addition, head width across temples immediately behind eyes 1.15 times as great as length of maxillary palpus (Fig. 71). Female features are given here for the first time.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Gansu).

Teledapalpus picatus (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**
(Figs 20, 23, 49, 55, 68, 79, 80)

Teledapalpus picatus Holzschuh, 2003: 149, Abb. 2 (type locality: China, C-Sichuan (Wenchuan), Jinding Shan, 31°25.6'N / 103°40.98'E, 3200 m (according to the original description)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 87; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♀, holotype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 23); 1♂ (cAM), 1♂ (cSM) (Fig. 20), China, Sichuan, Wenchuan City, SE of Dazhaizi Village, 2265 m, 31°27'10"N / 103°40'3"E, 26.06.2013 (leg. I.A. Belousov, I.I. Kabak, G.E. Davidian).

Morphological notes. Body length 10.7–13.8 or 16 mm in male and female, respectively.

Male (Fig. 20) closely resembles a female, but head larger, eyes more strongly developed; antennae longer, slightly not reaching the apex of elytra, most of antennomeres more elongated; terminal maxillary and labial palpomeres axe-shaped, as in Fig. 68; elytra narrower, as in Fig. 20; legs longer, tarsomere 1 more elongated; in addition, head width across temples immediately behind eyes 1.08 times as great as or subequal to length of maxillary palpus (Fig. 68); rudimentary wings as in Fig. 79. Male features are given here for the first time.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Sichuan).

Teledapalpus sp.
(Figs 48, 58, 67, 74, 80)

Remarks. Through the courtesy of Dr Nobuo Ohbayashi (Kamimiyada, Miura City, Japan), I studied high-quality photographs of this previously unknown species from Yunnan (Yingjiang County, Xima env., ~2000 m; Fig. 80) (Ohbayashi, Chou, in press).

Teledapalpus aranea (Holzschuh, 2003), **comb. n.**
(Figs 19, 47, 80)

Teledapalpus aranea Holzschuh, 2003: 150, Abb. 3 (type locality: N Vietnam, Hoang Lien Son Prov., Sapa env., Fan Si Pan, 22°18–25'N / 103°49–54'E, 2400 m (according to the original description)).

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 19).

Morphological notes. Body length 15.8 mm.

Remarks. Until now, this species is known only from the holotype.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Northern Vietnam.

Teledapalpus zolotichini Miroshnikov, 2000
(Figs 24, 52, 64, 72, 77, 80, 83)

Teledapalpus zolotichini Miroshnikov, 2000: 43, 47, fig. 33 (type locality: China, Shaanxi, Taibaishan National Park, 3000–3200 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 87; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cSM) (Fig. 24), China, Shaanxi, Taibaishan National Park, 3000–3200 m, 11–13.06.1999, pitfall trap (leg. S. Murzin); 1♀ (cSM), China, Shaanxi, Taibei Shan Mts, 3000 m, 18–21.06.2000 (leg. S. Murzin).

Morphological notes. Body length 12.7 or 15.4 mm in male and female, respectively.

Female closely resembles a male, but head smaller, eyes less strongly developed; antennae shorter, slightly reaching beyond the middle of elytra, most of antennomeres less elongated; terminal maxillary and labial palpomeres slenderer, not axe-shaped, as in Fig. 72; elytra wider, as in Fig. 83; legs shorter, tarsomere 1 less elongated; in addition, head width across temples immediately behind eyes 1.2 times as great as length of maxillary palpus (Fig. 72). Female features are given here for the first time.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Shaanxi).

Teledapalpus cremarius (Holzschuh, 1999)
(Figs 21, 50, 51, 65, 76, 80)

Teledapalpus cremarius Holzschuh, 1999: 6, 53 (Abb. 3) (type locality: China, Shaanxi, Qing Ling Shan, track Hou Zen Zi vill. to Taibai Shan, 3000 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)); Holzschuh, 2003: 149–151.

Teledapalpus cremarius: Miroshnikov, 2000: 44, 48, 50 figs 35, 36, 41.

Teledapalpus cremarius (misspelling): Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 86; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♂, holotype (cCH) (Fig. 21), China, Shaanxi prov., Qing Ling Shan, track Hou Zen Zi vill. to Taibai Shan, 3000 m, fir forest, 29.06–2.07.1998 (leg. Z. Jindra, O. Šafránek, M. Trýzna); 1♂ (cAM), same label.

Morphological notes. Body length 11.4–13.1 mm, thereby the holotype largest.

Remarks. Female unknown.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Shaanxi).

Teledalpus lobanovi Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**
(Figs 1, 22, 53, 66, 75, 78, 80, 82, 91)

Material. Holotype, ♂ (cSM) (Fig. 22): China, Sichuan Province, Maoxian County, SE Shangxinzhèn Village, 2935 m a.s.l., 31°34'32"N / 103°47'33"E, 3.07.2012 (leg. I.A. Belousov, G.E. Davidian).

Diagnosis. Based on male characters, this new species seems to be especially similar to *T. cremiarius* and *T. zolotichini*, but differs from both by the much shinier pronotal disc with a clearly more noticeable puncturation, not hidden by the recumbent setation, as in Fig. 53 (cf. Figs 51, 52) (in the compared species, the pronotal disc is poorly shiny, its puncturation is partly hidden by the recumbent setation and therefore can be seen weaker), the distinctly more elongated antennomere 3, as in Fig. 75 (cf. Figs 76, 77); in addition, differs from *T. cremiarius* by the less coarse puncturation of the elytra, the clearly less impressed area in the median part of the head behind the line connecting the lower margins of the upper lobes of the eyes, while from *T. zolotichini* by the scutellum being narrowed towards the apex (in *T. zolotichini*, the scutellum is rounded apically). *Teledalpus lobanovi* **sp. n.** can also be compared to *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.**, but is distinguished by the clearly denser and coarser puncturation of the elytra, the absence of a smooth, shiny, longitudinal, median line on most of the pronotum, as in Fig. 53 (cf. Fig. 56), the more elongated antennomere 3 and tarsomere 1 at least of the metatarsus (taking into account the supposed length of these segments in an unknown female of a new species).

Description. Male. Body length 14.3 mm, basal width at level of scutellum apex 2.7 mm. Head dorsally, pronotum, meso- and metasterna, abdomen, femora, and tibiae dark reddish brown; elytra, scutellum, head ventrally, prosternum reddish brown; antennae almost entirely and tarsi brownish; palps brownish yellow; eyes and partly mandibles black; elytra strongly shiny.

Head mostly with a rough, dense and confluent puncturation dorsally, with a distinct, narrow, median groove between bases of antennae and partly eyes; antennal tubercles moderately developed; genae short, distinctly shorter than protarsomere 2; submentum mainly with well-expressed transversal wrinkles; head width across temples immediately behind eyes subequal to length of maxillary palpus; terminal maxillary and labial palpomeres axe-shaped, as in Figs 53, 66; antennae slender, slightly not reaching the apex of elytra; length ratio of antennomeres 1–11, 26 : 10 : 33 : 26 : 37 : 31 : 30 : 26 : 22 : 22 : 22; antennomere 2 distinctly longitudinal.

Pronotum oblong, 1.57 times as long as width at base; at apex slightly narrower than at base; with a well-expressed constriction before base and near apex; lateral tubercles strongly developed, as in Figs 22, 53; with a very distinct, somewhat heterogeneous, partly rough, mainly dense and confluent puncturation, being rarefied in a small area of central part of disc, with a very short, narrow, longitudinal, smooth (devoid of punctures), median line before middle.

Scutellum triangular, rounded apically, with distinct dense punctures.

Elytra elongate, 3.4 times as long as basal width at level of scutellum apex; slightly and partly roundly widened towards apical third starting from humeri, then roundly narrowed towards apex; clearly convex on disc; each elytron near base distinctly impressed; with a rough, somewhat irregular, partly very dense puncturation being somewhat weakened towards apex.

Rudimentary wings as in Figs 78, 82.

Prosternum, mostly in median part, meso- and metasterna with a distinct, mainly very dense puncturation, prosternum in apical third mostly with a smooth and strongly shiny sculpture; prosternal process very narrow between procoxae; mesosternal

process quite wide at base, strongly narrowed towards apex, noticeably convex; abdominal sternites with a very small, but distinct, dense and very dense puncturation; last (visible) sternite truncate apically; last (visible) tergite rounded at apex.

Legs long and slender; tarsomere 1 relatively strongly elongate, metatarsomere 1 about 2.2 times as long as next two combined.

Elytra with numerous, long, erect setae; head and pronotum clothed with similar, but sparse setae; venter and legs with more or less long, erect and suberect setae being the most numerous on meso- and metatibiae, and metafemora.

Female unknown.

Bionomics. The holotype was taken during a night catch on the trunk of one of the low deciduous trees growing near the upper border of the forest at an altitude of about 3000 m (Fig. 1) (in the photograph, these two trees are located in the foreground on the right).

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Sichuan).

Etymology. This new species is dedicated to the memory of my friend and colleague, Andrei Lvovich Lobanov (1940–2020), a famous Russian coleopterologist who was the creator and permanent web editor of the grandiose and unique site “Beetles (Coleoptera) and coleopterists” (<http://zin.ru/Animalia/Coleoptera/rus/index.html>).

Teledalpus pilosellus (Holzschuh, 2007), **comb. n.**
(Figs 26, 56, 80)

Teledalpus pilosellus Holzschuh, 2007: 181 (type locality: “China, C-Sichuan, Jintang, Jialin Shan, 30°22'451"N, 102°16'644"E, 2300 m” (according to the original description)); Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Chen et al., 2019: 87; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Material. 1♀, holotype (cCH) (photograph; Fig. 26).

Morphological notes. Body length 13.5 mm.

Remarks. Until now, this species is known only from the holotype.

The type locality, including the coordinates indicated in the original publication [Holzschuh, 2007], in my opinion, should be clarified. Here it is taken as follows: China, Sichuan, Jintang, Jiajin Shan, 2300 m, 30°22'N / 102°16'E.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Sichuan).

Teledalpus daliensis Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**
(Figs 29, 57, 73, 80)

Material. Holotype, ♀ (SMNS) (Fig. 29): China, Yunnan Province, Dali Bay Autonomous Prefecture, Diancang Shan Mts, above Dali, 2500–2700 m a.s.l., 25°41'N / 100°06'E, 8–18.04.1999 (leg. W. Schawaller). Paratype: 1♀ (cAM), same label.

Diagnosis. Based on female characters, this new species is distinguished from almost all congeners in the structure of the pronotum, in particular, the less sharp constriction near the apex and in front of the base and the less strongly developed lateral tubercles, as in Figs 29, 57 (cf. Figs 44–46, 48–56, 58, 61), as well as by the somewhat shorter temples compared with the females of *T. zolotichini*, *T. picatus* **comb. n.**, *T. hospes*, as in Fig. 57 (cf. Figs 54, 55), while from a female of *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.** differs by the absence of a smooth, longitudinal, median line of the pronotum, as in Fig. 57 (cf. Fig. 56), the shorter erect setae, and the coarser and denser puncturation of the elytra. *Teledalpus*

Figs 21–25. Species of *Teledalpus*, habitus, dorsal view.
 21 – *T. cremiarius*; 22 – *T. lobanovi* sp. n.; 23 – *T. picatus* comb. n.; 24 – *T. zolotichini*; 25 – *T. hospes*. 21–24 – holotypes; 21–22, 24 – males; 23, 25 – females (21, 23 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).
 Рис. 21–25. Виды рода *Teledalpus*, общий вид сверху.
 21 – *T. cremiarius*; 22 – *T. lobanovi* sp. n.; 23 – *T. picatus* comb. n.; 24 – *T. zolotichini*; 25 – *T. hospes*. 21–24 – голотипы; 21–22, 24 – самцы; 23, 25 – самки (21, 23 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

Figs 26–30. Species of *Teledalpus* and *Parateledapus*, holotypes, habitus, dorsal view.

26 – *T. pilosellus* comb. n.; 27 – *T. transitivus* sp. n.; 28 – *T. linyejiei* comb. n., male (after Huang et al. [2021]); 29 – *T. daliensis* sp. n.; 30 – *P. gibbus*.
26–27, 29–30 – females (26, 30 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 26–30. Виды родов *Teledalpus* и *Parateledapus*, голотипы, общий вид сверху.

26 – *T. pilosellus* comb. n.; 27 – *T. transitivus* sp. n.; 28 – *T. linyejiei* comb. n., самец (по [Huang et al., 2021]); 29 – *T. daliensis* sp. n.; 30 – *P. gibbus*.
26–27, 29–30 – самки (26, 30 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

Figs 31–37. Species of *Teledapus*, males, head, dorsal view, and pronotum.
 31–32 – *T. dorcadioides*; 33 – *T. ocularis*; 34–35 – *T. querceti*; 36–37 – *T. celsicola*. 32–34, 36 – holotypes; 35, 37 – paratypes (33–37 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 31–37. Виды рода *Teledapus*, самцы, голова сверху и переднеспинка.
 31–32 – *T. dorcadioides*; 33 – *T. ocularis*; 34–35 – *T. querceti*; 36–37 – *T. celsicola*. 32–34, 36 – голотипы; 35, 37 – паратипы (33–37 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

Figs 38–43. Species of *Teledapus*, females, head, dorsal view, and pronotum.

38 – *T. dorcadioides*; 39 – *T. ocularis*; 40, 43 – *T. querceti*; 41–42 – *T. celsicola*. 39, 41–43 – paratypes (39–43 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 38–43. Виды рода *Teledapus*, самки, голова сверху и переднеспинка.

38 – *T. dorcadioides*; 39 – *T. ocularis*; 40, 43 – *T. querceti*; 41–42 – *T. celsicola*. 39, 41–43 – паратипы (39–43 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

daliensis sp. n. is similar to *T. aranea* comb. n. (Figs 19, 47) in the degree of development of the lateral tubercles of pronotum, but differs from it by the clearly more sloping humeri, as in Fig. 29 (cf. Fig. 19), the shorter at least maxillary palps, as in Figs 57, 73 (cf. Fig. 47), the less elongated tarsomeres 1 and 2, as in Fig. 29 (cf. Fig. 19) (taking into account the supposed length of the palps and tarsomeres in an unknown female of a compared species).

Description. Female. Body length 16.7–17.2 mm, basal width at level of scutellum apex 3.5–3.6 mm.

Colouration of integument mainly combines dark reddish brown and reddish brown tones, while pronotum mostly darkest; palps red-yellow; protarsi partly reddish; eyes, partly mandibles, and margins of genae black.

Head mostly with a rough, very dense and confluent puncturation dorsally, with a distinct, narrow, median groove between bases of antennae and partly eyes; antennal tubercles moderately developed; genae subequal to longitudinal eye diameter; submentum with well-expressed transversal wrinkles; head width across temples immediately behind eyes 1.23–1.25 times as great as length of maxillary palpus; antennae slender, about reaching the middle of elytra; length ratio of antennomeres 1–11, 26 : 9 : 27 : 22 : 28 : 22 : 22 : 18 : 17 : 16 : 17 (holotype taken as an example); antennomere 2 distinctly longitudinal.

Pronotum oblong, 1.26 times as long as width at base; at apex slightly narrower than at base; with a poorly expressed constriction before base and near apex; lateral tubercles relatively weakly developed, as in Figs 29, 57; very distinctly convex on disc; with a very clear, somewhat heterogeneous, partly rough, mainly dense and confluent puncturation.

Scutellum transverse, triangular, strongly narrowed towards apex, with distinct dense punctures.

Elytra elongate-oval, 3.14 times as long as basal width at level of scutellum apex; distinctly and roundly widened towards middle starting from humeri, then roundly narrowed towards apex; slightly convex on disc; with a relatively coarse, more or less regular, mainly uniform puncturation being distinctly weakened towards apex.

Prosternum in median part with a small, very dense puncturation, in apical third with distinct transverse wrinkles; prosternal process quite narrow between procoxae; meso- and metasterna with a distinct, small, partly wrinkly, very dense and confluent puncturation; mesosternal process quite wide at base, strongly narrowed towards apex; abdominal sternites with distinct, small, dense punctures; last (visible) sternite clearly emarginate apically; last (visible) tergite subtruncate at apex.

Legs long and slender; tarsomere I relatively strongly elongate, metatarsomere 1, 1.47 times as long as next two combined.

Elytra with numerous, moderately long, erect and suberect setae being gradually shortened towards apex; head, pronotum, venter, femora and tibiae clothed with more or less long, erect and suberect setae of varying density.

Male unknown.

Remarks. The paratype is badly damaged (crushed).

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Yunnan).

Etymology. This species name refers to the type locality.

Teledapalpus transitivus Miroshnikov, **sp. n.**

(Figs 27, 61, 62, 80)

Material. Holotype, ♀ (cSM) (Fig. 27): China, Yunnan Province, Deqen (Deqin) County, NE slope of SE Baima Mt. Ridge, SW of Benzilanzhen Village, 3225 m a.s.l., 28°10'44"N / 99°14'28"E, 5.06.2013 (leg. I.A. Belousov, I.I. Kabak, G.E. Davidian).

Diagnosis. The new species combines some of the features of both *Teledapalpus* and *Teledapus* and therefore to be considered as a transitional (intermediate) form. Nevertheless, due to the comparatively slender body of the female, including the pronotum and elytra, and the comparatively large eyes, it appears more similar to the representatives of *Teledapalpus*. *Teledapalpus transitivus* **sp. n.** is distinguished from all congeners, at least in comparison with their females, by the short maxillary and labial palps, as in Figs 61, 62, the somewhat peculiar shape of the elytra, as in Fig. 27, the comparatively short basal tarsomere, as well as by some other features.

Description. Female. Body length 17.5 mm, basal width at level of scutellum apex 2.9 mm.

Colouration of integument mainly combines dark reddish brown and reddish brown tones, while dorsum mostly darkest; palps red-yellow; eyes, mandibles, and margins of genae black.

Head mostly with a distinct, dense and confluent puncturation dorsally, with a narrow, median groove between bases of antennae and eyes; antennal tubercles weakly developed; genae moderately short, slightly longer than protarsomere 2; submentum mostly with gentle transversal wrinkles; head width across temples immediately behind eyes about 1.7 times as great as length of maxillary palpus; antennae slender, distinctly not reaching the middle of elytra; length ratio of antennomeres 1–11, 23 : 8 : 23 : 17 : 22 : 17 : 18 : 14 : 14 : 13 : 15; antennomere 2 slightly longitudinal.

Pronotum oblong, 1.27 times as long as width at base; at apex slightly narrower than at base; with a well-expressed constriction before base and near apex; lateral tubercles moderately developed, as in Figs 27, 61; with a distinct, somewhat heterogeneous, partly rough, mainly dense and confluent puncturation, with a short, elongate-oval, smooth (devoid of punctures), median line before middle.

Scutellum triangular, rounded apically, with distinct punctures.

Elytra of a somewhat peculiar shape, as in Fig. 27, elongate, relatively narrow in humeri, about 3.6 times as long as basal width at level of scutellum apex; very distinctly and partly roundly widened towards apical third starting from humeri, then roundly narrowed towards apex; on disc mainly depressed; with a rough, more or less regular, mainly uniform puncturation being somewhat weakened towards apex.

Prosternum mainly in median part with a distinct rugose sculpture; prosternal process quite narrow between procoxae; meso- and metasterna with a distinct, partly wrinkly, very dense and confluent puncturation; mesosternal process at base moderately wide, strongly narrowed towards apex, noticeably convex; abdominal sternites with a small, distinct, dense and very dense puncturation; last (visible) sternite broadly rounded apically, last (visible) tergite subtruncate at apex.

Legs slender and moderately long; metatarsomere 1 slightly longer than next two combined.

Dorsum with numerous (especially so on elytra), long, erect setae; venter and legs clothed with long, erect and suberect, partly more or less numerous setae.

Male unknown.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Yunnan).

Etymology. The name of this species is given so that to show the transitional character of the taxon from the genus *Teledapalpus* to *Teledapus* based of female features.

Teledapalpus linyejiei

(Huang, Li et Zhang, 2021), **comb. n.**

(Figs 28, 59, 60, 80)

Teledapus linyejiei Huang, Li et Zhang, 2021: 441, 443, figs 1–6 (type locality: China, Yunnan Province, Diqing Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Weixi Lisu Autonomous County, Weideng Township (according to the original description)).

Material. 1♂, holotype (LPSNU) (photograph; Fig. 28).

Remarks. Due to the large eyes, the comparatively short temples (Figs 59, 60), and taking into account the ratio of the head width at the level of the temples immediately behind the eyes to the length of the maxillary palpus, this species resembles *Teledapalpus* more than *Teledapus*. Therefore, it seems justified to me to transfer it to the former genus as *Teledapalpus linyejiei* **comb. n.**

In general, the dichromatic colouration of the elytra in combination with some other features, including the moderately long maxillary palps (Figs 59, 60), the longest rudimentary wings [Huang et al., 2021: Fig. 6] in comparison with other congeners (Figs 78, 79, 81–84), makes this abnormal species quite peculiar morphologically.

Female unknown.

Morphological notes. Body length 14.8–15.4 mm, thereby holotype smallest.

Distribution (Fig. 80). China (Yunnan).

Key to species of the genus *Teledapalpus*

1. Elytral integument monochrome, without pattern, only epipleurae usually lighter than the rest of surface 2
- Elytral integument bicoloured, with a peculiar pattern, as in Fig. 28 (female unknown) *T. linyejiei* **comb. n.**
2. Maxillary and labial palps distinctly longer, as, for example, in Figs 54–58, 71–74, thereby head width across temples immediately behind eyes not more than 1.3 times as great as length of maxillary palpus;

- female elytra wider at base, of one shape or another, as in Figs 23, 25, 26, 29; antennae of female about reaching the middle of elytra or reaching beyond it, as in Figs 23, 25, 26, 29 3
- Maxillary and labial palps distinctly shorter, as in Figs 61, 62, thereby head width across temples immediately behind eyes about 1.7 times as great as length of maxillary palpus; female elytra comparatively narrower at base, of a somewhat peculiar shape, as in Fig. 27; antennae of female distinctly not reaching the middle of elytra, as in Fig. 27 (male unknown) *T. transitivus* **sp. n.**
3. Pronotum with less strongly expressed constrictions at apex and in front of base, with less strongly developed lateral tubercles, as in Figs 47, 57 4
- Pronotum with more strongly expressed constrictions at apex and in front of base, with a more strongly developed lateral tubercles, as in Figs 44–46, 48–56, 58 5
4. Humeri less clearly sloping, humeral angle distinctly expressed, as in Fig. 19; at least maxillary palps distinctly longer, as in Figs 19, 47 (taking into account supposed length of palps in unknown female); tarsomeres 1 and 2 distinctly more elongated, as in Fig. 19 (Vietnam) *T. aranea* **comb. n.**
- Humeri more clearly sloping, humeral angle not expressed, as in Fig. 29; at least maxillary palps distinctly shorter, as in Figs 29, 57, 73 (taking into account supposed length of palps in unknown male); tarsomeres 1 and 2 distinctly less elongated, as in Fig. 29 (China) *T. daliensis* **sp. n.**
5. Temples one way or another roundly sloping backwards or only partly (but not more than halfway) more or less straight, usually slightly shorter, as in Figs 44–47, 49–53, 54–56, 64–66, 71–73; antennae of male shorter than body, in female about reaching the middle of elytra or freely reaching beyond it 6
- Temples mostly almost straight, rather long, as in Figs 48, 58, 67, 74; antennae of male longer than body, in female almost reaching or reaching the last quarter of elytra *Teledapalpus* **sp.**
6. Elytra without long erect setae or at most with sparse long erect setae 7
- Elytra with numerous long, erect setae 10
7. Elytra with a dull sheen, without long erect setae; pronotum without clear, smooth, shiny, longitudinal, median line on most of it, as in Figs 44–46, 54 8
- Elytra very distinctly shiny, with sparse, long, erect setae; pronotum with a smooth, shiny, longitudinal, median line on most of it, as in Figs 49, 55 *T. picatus* **comb. n.**
8. Elytra narrower, less strongly widened towards apex, starting from base, as in Figs 15, 16; submentum to some extent with legibly expressed transversal wrinkles 9
- Elytra wider, more strongly widened towards apex, starting from base, as in Figs 17, 18, 25; submentum with coarse puncturation, without distinct transversal wrinkles *T. hospes*
9. Male antennae longer, about reaching last sixth of elytra, as in Fig. 15; mesosternal process narrowed [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, fig. 6]; sculpture of pro-, meso- and metasterna noticeably coarser; abdominal

- sternites with distinct punctures (female unknown) *T. murzini*
- Male antennae shorter, about reaching last third of elytra, as in Fig. 16; mesosternal process wider [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, fig. 7]; sculpture of pro-, meso- and metasterna noticeably less coarse; abdominal sternites with weak, less distinct punctures (female unknown) .. *T. zamotajlovi*
10. Pronotum without broad, smooth, shiny, median, longitudinal line on most of it, as in Figs 50–53 11
- Pronotum with a wide, smooth, shiny, median, longitudinal line on most of it, as in Fig. 56 (male unknown) *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.**
11. Antennomere 3 less elongated, as in Figs 76, 77; pronotal disc poorly shiny, its puncturation partly hidden by recumbent setation being less distinctly visible, at least so in male, as in Figs 50–52 12
- Antennomere 3 more elongated, as in Fig. 75; pronotal disc very clearly shiny, its puncturation not hidden by recumbent setation being more distinctly visible, as in Fig. 53 (female unknown) *T. lobanovi* **sp. n.**
12. Elytra with more coarse rugosity; scutellum narrowed towards apex, triangular [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, fig. 8]; last (visible) abdominal sternite of male rounded apically [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, fig. 10]; puncturation on temples somewhat more coarse than on genae, this difference being very faint (female unknown) *T. cremiarius*
- Elytra with less coarse rugosity; scutellum rounded apically [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, Fig. 9]; last (visible) abdominal sternite of male truncate apically [Miroshnikov, 2000: 42, fig. 11]; border between coarse puncturation on temples and much more less coarse puncturation on genae clearly expressed, at least so in male *T. zolotichini*

Genus *Parateledapus* Miroshnikov, 2000

Parateledapus Miroshnikov, 2000: 44; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017: 172.

Type species *Teledapus gibbus* Holzschuh, 1989, by original designation.

Diagnosis. This genus is distinguished from *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus* in many features, including the structure of the head, pronotum, and elytra (details these differences see Miroshnikov [2000]).

Composition. The genus includes one species.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Indochina (Thailand).

Parateledapus gibbus (Holzschuh, 1989)
(Figs 30, 80)

Teledapus gibbus Holzschuh, 1989: 363, Abb. 2, 11 (type locality: Thailand, Doi Inthanon, 2500 m (according to the original description and the label of the holotype)).

Parateledapus gibbus: Miroshnikov, 2000: 49–50, 53, figs 39, 42.

Material. 1♀, holotype (cCH) (Fig. 30), Thailande, Doi Inthanon, 2500 m, 9.02.1985, tamisage (gesiebt) (leg. P. Schwendinger).

Morphological notes. Body length 16.9 mm.

Remarks. Until now, this species is known only from the holotype.

Distribution (Fig. 80). Northern Thailand.

Figs 44–48. Species of *Teledalpalpus*, males, head, dorsal view, and pronotum.
 44 – *T. murzini*; 45 – *T. zamotajlovi*; 46 – *T. hospes*; 47 – *T. aranea* **comb. n.**; 48 – *Teledalpalpus* sp. (Yunnan, China; photograph by Nobuo Ohbayashi).
 44–47 – holotypes (46–47 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 44–48. Виды рода *Teledalpalpus*, самцы, голова сверху и переднеспинка.
 44 – *T. murzini*; 45 – *T. zamotajlovi*; 46 – *T. hospes*; 47 – *T. aranea* **comb. n.**; 48 – *Teledalpalpus* sp. (Юньнань, Китай; фотография Н. Обаяси).
 44–47 – голотипы (46–47 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

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Figs 49–53. Species of *Teledalpalus*, males, head, dorsal view, and pronotum.

49 – *T. picatus* **comb. n.**; 50–51 – *T. cremiarius* (50 – photograph by Luboš Dembický); 52 – *T. zolotichini*; 53 – *T. lobanovi* **sp. n.** 50, 52–53 – holotypes.

Рис. 49–53. Виды рода *Teledalpalus*, самцы, голова сверху и переднеспинка.

49 – *T. picatus* **comb. n.**; 50–51 – *T. cremiarius* (50 – фотография Л. Дембицкого); 52 – *T. zolotichini*; 53 – *T. lobanovi* **sp. n.** 50, 52–53 – голотипы.

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Figs 54–58. Species of *Teledalpus*, females, head, dorsal view, and pronotum.

54 – *T. hospes*; 55 – *T. picatus* **comb. n.**; 56 – *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.**; 57 – *T. daliensis* **sp. n.**; 58 – *Teledalpus* sp. (Yunnan, China; photograph by Nobuo Ohbayashi). 55–57 – holotypes (55–56 – photographs by Luboš Dembický).

Рис. 54–58. Виды рода *Teledalpus*, самки, голова сверху и переднеспинка.

54 – *T. hospes*; 55 – *T. picatus* **comb. n.**; 56 – *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.**; 57 – *T. daliensis* **sp. n.**; 58 – *Teledalpus* sp. (Юньнань, Китай; фотография Н. Обаяси). 55–57 – голотипы (55–56 – фотографии Л. Дембицкого).

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Figs 59–62. Species of *Teledapalpus*, holotypes.

59–60 – *T. linyejiei* **comb. n.**, male (after Huang et al. [2021]); 61–62 – *T. transitivus* **sp. n.**, female. 59, 61 – head, dorsal view, and pronotum; 60, 62 – head, ventral view.

Рис. 59–62. Виды рода *Teledapalpus*, голотипы.

59–60 – *T. linyejiei* **comb. n.**, самец (по [Huang et al., 2021]); 61–62 – *T. transitivus* **sp. n.**, самка. 59, 61 – голова сверху и переднеспинка; 60, 62 – голова снизу.

Figs 63–68. Species of *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*, males, head, ventral view.
 63 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 64 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 65 – *Teledapalpus cremiarius*; 66 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n.; 67 – *Teledapalpus* sp. (Yunnan, China; photograph by Nobuo Ohbayashi); 68 – *Teledapalpus picatus* comb. n. 64, 66 – holotypes.
 Рис. 63–68. Виды родов *Teledapus* и *Teledapalpus*, самцы, голова снизу.
 63 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 64 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 65 – *Teledapalpus cremiarius*; 66 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n.; 67 – *Teledapalpus* sp. (Юньнань, Китай; фотография Н. Обаяси); 68 – *Teledapalpus picatus* comb. n. 64, 66 – голотипы.

Figs 69–74. Species of *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*, females, head, ventral view.
 69 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 70 – *Teledapus querceti* (photograph by Luboš Dembičský); 71 – *Teledapalpus hospes*; 72 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 73 – *Teledapalpus daliensis* sp. n., holotype; 74 – *Teledapalpus* sp. (Yunnan, China; photograph by Nobuo Ohbayashi).
 Рис. 69–74. Виды родов *Teledapus* и *Teledapalpus*, самки, голова снизу.
 69 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 70 – *Teledapus querceti* Holzschuh, 2007 (фотография Л. Дембицкого); 71 – *Teledapalpus hospes*; 72 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 73 – *Teledapalpus daliensis* sp. n., голотип; 74 – *Teledapalpus* sp. (Юньнань, Китай; фотография Н. Обаяси).

Figs 75–79. Species of *Teledalpalpus*, details of structure.

75, 78 – *T. lobanovi* sp. n.; 76 – *T. cremiarius*; 77 – *T. zolotichini*; 79 – *T. picatus* comb. n. 75, 77–78 – holotypes; 75–77 – left antennomeres 2–5; 78–79 – right wing and body part, dorsal view.

Рис. 75–79. Виды рода *Teledalpalpus*, детали строения.

75, 78 – *T. lobanovi* sp. n.; 76 – *T. cremiarius*; 77 – *T. zolotichini*; 79 – *T. picatus* comb. n. 75, 77–78 – голотипы; 75–77 – левые 2–5-й членики усиков; 78–79 – правое крыло и часть тела сверху.

Discussion of the taxonomy, diagnostic characters, and distribution of the tribe representatives

Teledapus and *Teledalpalpus*, morphologically very similar, represent the taxonomically complex group. However, despite the fact that the transitional or even abnormal state of certain characters are demonstrated by some representatives of these genera, the vast majority of their species have characteristic generic traits. Distinguishing features of the genera *Teledapus* and *Teledalpalpus* are presented in Table 2.

All four species of *Teledapus* are typical members of the genus. Among their most characteristic and stable features are comparatively small eyes, as in Figs 31–43, comparatively short palps, as in Figs 31–43, 63, 69, 70, and the ratio of the head width across the temples immediately

behind the eyes to the length of the maxillary palpus (1.3–1.4 in males, 1.5–1.75 in females; Table 2).

The vast majority of *Teledalpalpus* species are typical representatives of the genus. Among their most characteristic and stable traits are comparatively large eyes, as in Figs 44–59, 61, comparatively long palps, as in Figs 44–58, 64–68, 71–74, and the ratio of head width across the temples immediately behind the eyes to the length of the maxillary palpus (0.7–1.1 in the known males, 0.98–1.25 in the known females; Table 2). Only in the male of *Teledalpalpus linyejiei* comb. n. displaying some abnormal characters, the indicated ratio is about 1.2 (Fig. 60), while in the female of *T. transitivus* sp. n. with a transitional state of the genus-rank features – about 1.7 (Fig. 62).

Species of *Teledapus* are mainly restricted to the Himalayas, moreover, three out of four, namely *T. dorcadioides*, *T. querceti* and *T. ocularis*, originate only

from the western part of this mountain system (Fig. 80, localities 1–9). The only species, *T. celsicola*, inhabits the Hengduan Mountains (Sino-Tibetan Mountains), adjacent to the eastern extremities of the Himalayas, and is only known from the type locality in the Markam County (Tibet Autonomous Region) (Fig. 80, locality 10). In the eastern part of the Himalayas, representatives of this genus have not yet been recorded.

All typical *Teledapalpus* species are only known from the south of Gansu (*T. hospes*) and Shaanxi (*T. zolotichini*, *T. cremiarius*), the northern and central parts of Sichuan (*T. murzini*, *T. zamotajlovi*, *T. lobanovi* **sp. n.**, *T. picatus* **comb. n.**, *T. pilosellus* **comb. n.**), the areas of Yunnan, which are significantly distant from the eastern extremities of the Himalayas (*T. daliensis* **sp. n.**, *Teledapalpus* sp.), and further south, in particular, from Northern Vietnam (*T. aranea* **comb. n.**) (Fig. 80, localities 11–20, 23–25).

In the extreme northwest of Yunnan, in the Hengduan Mountains, it seems there is an intergradation zone for *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*. Exactly there, the specific individual forms, such as *Teledapalpus transitivus* **sp. n.**, with the most pronounced transitional state of traits, were found (Fig. 80, locality 21). It is not by accident that in the same area, another peculiar species, *Teledapalpus lineyiei* **comb. n.**, with some abnormal characters hitherto unrecorded neither in *Teledapus* nor in *Teledapalpus*, in particular, a bicolourate pattern of the elytral integument, was discovered (Fig. 80, locality 22). The zone of intergradation, most likely, also covers the extreme southwestern parts of Sichuan, the extreme southeastern parts of the Tibet Autonomous Region adjoining to the northwest Yunnan, and the adjacent extreme northern areas of Myanmar, all in the same Hengduan Mountains area.

However, not all species from the intergradation zone appear transitional and abnormal forms. In particular, as noted afore, *T. celsicola*, a quite typical representative of *Teledapus* occurs here. Consequently, not only new transitional and unusual forms, but also new typical *Teledapus* and, probably, *Teledapalpus*, can be expected in this complex geographical area.

At the same time, it seems extremely important to state that none of the typical representatives of the genus *Teledapalpus* has yet been found in the Himalayas, i.e., within the boundaries of the main distribution area of *Teledapus*, and none of the *Teledapus* species has been recorded within the distribution range of the typical *Teledapalpus*, i.e., in the south of Gansu and Shaanxi, the northern and central parts of Sichuan, the part of Yunnan, significantly distant from the eastern extremities of the Himalayas, or further south, in Indochina. This fact, it seems, testifies to the quite obvious delimitation of the distribution area of the two genera, despite the presence of individual transitive and abnormal forms in the intergradation zone roughly outlined above.

The genera *Teledapus* and *Teledapalpus*, with little doubt, descended from the same ancestor, but to date have not yet undergone a distinct division of the generic characters in all congeners. *Parateledapus* most likely descended from the same ancestor as well. It has

already reached a very distinct grade of morphological differentiation, but its distribution is so far limited only by the type locality in Northern Thailand (Fig. 80, locality 26). The existence of the latter genus can be considered a weighty additional argument in favor of the validity of *Teledapalpus* as a good genus, contrary to the opinion of some researchers who place all Teledapini in a single genus *Teledapus* [Holzschuh, 1981, 1989, 1999, 2003, 2007].

It seems obvious to me that the genera *Teledapus*, *Teledapalpus* and *Parateledapus* form a monophyletic group, deservedly distinguished into the tribe Teledapini and clearly differing from the tribe Xylosteini. This opinion of mine was kindly announced in part by Dr Nobuo Ohbayashi [Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017], with whom I discussed the present taxonomic issue in a personal communication. Distinguishing features of the tribes Xylosteini and Teledapini are presented in Table 1.

Tribe Xylosteini Reitter, 1913

Xylosteina Reitter, 1913: 5.

Xylosteini: Plavilstshikov, 1936: 107, 493; Gressitt, 1951: 47; Gressitt, Rondon, 1970: 26; Miroshnikov, 1998: 8; Miroshnikov, 2000: 37; Miroshnikov, 2004: 109; Bousquet et al., 2009: 23; Catalogue..., 2010: 136; Bouchard et al., 2011: 464; Bi, Ohbayashi, 2014: 6; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017: 171–172; Kariyanna et al., 2017: 258; Chen et al., 2019: 87; Catalogue..., 2020: 180.

Type genus *Xylosteus* Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1838.

Diagnosis. This tribe is most similar to Teledapini, but differs in the features noted in Table 1.

Composition. The generic composition of this tribe has changed many times and has been considered differently by various researchers [Reitter, 1913; Plavilstshikov, 1936; Gressitt, 1951; Gressitt, Rondon, 1970; Miroshnikov, 2000; Catalogue..., 2010, and others].

According to the relatively recent publications [Bi, Ohbayashi, 2014; Ohbayashi, Tichý, 2017], the tribe includes the following genera:

Xylosteus Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1838,
Leptorhabdium Kraatz, 1879,
Notorhabdium N. Ohbayashi et Shimomura, 1986,
Palaeoxylosteus N. Ohbayashi et Shimomura, 1986,
Pseudoxylosteus Sama, 1993,
Chiangshunania Bi et N. Ohbayashi, 2014,
Niisatoa N. Ohbayashi et Tichý, 2017.

In the present work, this generic composition of the tribe is accepted and followed.

Remarks. The systematic position of the genus *Peithona* Gahan, 1906 has not yet been clarified, which has already been noted by some authors [Bi, Ohbayashi, 2014]. However, in the latest Palaeartic and Chinese catalogues [Catalogue..., 2020; Chen et al., 2019], this genus is listed, as before [Catalogue..., 2010], in the tribe Xylosteini.

A preliminary study of the adults morphology and some features of the larvae [Insect Forum, <http://insectforum.no-ip.org/gods/cgi-bin/view.cgi?forum=2&topic=29626>] of *Peithona prionoides* Gahan, 1906 demonstrated that, in my opinion, it would be advisable to establish a separate new tribe for the genus *Peithona*. However, this question requires additional careful examination and is beyond the scope of present work.

Fig. 80. Geographical distribution of the Teledapini species. The locality numbers correspond to the numbers and names of localities in Table 3; circle – localities of *Teledapus* species, triangle – localities of *Teledalpalpus* species, square – locality of *Parateledapus gibbus*.

Рис. 80. Географическое распространение видов трибы Teledapini. Номера местонахождений соответствуют номерам и названиям местонахождений в таблице 3; круг – местонахождения видов *Teledapus*, треугольник – местонахождения видов *Teledalpalpus*, квадрат – местонахождение *Parateledapus gibbus*.

Table 3. Localities and the corresponding Teledapini species.

Таблица 3. Местонахождения и соответствующие виды Teledapini.

No	Locality / Местонахождение	Species / Вид
1	Pakistan, Sari (= Siri), Shogran env., 2750–2900 m, 34°37'N / 73°29'E	<i>Teledapus ocularis</i>
2	Pakistan, Hazara, Kaghan Valley, Kaghan, 3000 m, 34°46'N / 73°30'E	<i>Teledapus ocularis</i>
3	Pakistan, Lalazar, 3000 m, 34°55'N / 73°46'E	<i>Teledapus ocularis</i>
4	India, Himachal Pradesh, Shimla (= Simla), 2200 m, 31°06'N / 77°10'E	<i>Teledapus dorcadoides</i>
5	India, Uttarakhand, Deoban, Jaunsar, 2300 m, 30°45'N / 77°50'E	<i>Teledapus dorcadoides</i>
6	India, Uttarakhand, Chakrata, 2100 m, 30°42'N / 77°52'E	<i>Teledapus dorcadoides</i>
7	India, Uttarakhand, Mussoorie, 1900 m, 30°27'N / 78°04'E	<i>Teledapus dorcadoides</i>
8	India, Uttarakhand, Wan, 2800 m, 30°12'N / 79°37'E	<i>Teledapus querceti</i>
9	India, Uttarakhand, Mundoli (= Mandoli) – Lohajang, 2600 m, 30°08'N / 79°36'E	<i>Teledapus querceti</i>
10	China, Tibet, road Yanjing – Markam, 50 km S Markam, 4400 m, 29°16'N / 98°38'E	<i>Teledapus celsicola</i>
11	China, Gansu, 70 km W of Wudu, 1800–2500 m, 33°30'N / 104°35'E	<i>Teledalpalpus hospes</i>
12	China, Shaanxi, Qing Ling Shan, track Hou Zen Zi Villige to Taibai Shan, 3000 m, 33°57'N / 107°37'E	<i>Teledalpalpus cremiarius</i>
13	China, Shaanxi, Taibei Shan Mts, 3000 m, 33°52'N / 107°42'E	<i>Teledalpalpus zolotichini</i>
14	China, Shaanxi, Taibaishan National Park, 3000–3200 m, 33°57'N / 107°45'E	<i>Teledalpalpus zolotichini</i>
15	China, Sichuan, Nanping env., 3500 m, 33°15'N / 104°13'E	<i>Teledalpalpus murzini</i>
16	China, Sichuan, Juizhaigou, 4000 m, 33°11'N / 104°07'E	<i>Teledalpalpus zamotajlovi</i>
17	China, Sichuan, Maoxian County, SE Shangxinzheng Village, 2935 m, 31°34'32"N / 103°47'33"E	<i>Teledalpalpus lobanovi</i> sp. n.
18	China, Sichuan, Wenchuan City, SE of Dazhaizi Village, 2265 m, 31°27'10"N / 103°40'3"E	<i>Teledalpalpus picatus</i>
19	China, Sichuan, Wenchuan City, Jinding Shan, 3200 m, 31°25'N / 103°40'E	<i>Teledalpalpus picatus</i>
20	China, Sichuan, Jintang, Jiajin Shan, 2300 m, 30°22'N / 102°16'E	<i>Teledalpalpus pilosellus</i>
21	China, Yunnan, Deqen (Deqin) County, NE slope of SE Baima Mt. Ridge, SW of Benzilanzenh Village, 3225 m, 28°10'44"N / 99°14'28"E	<i>Teledalpalpus transitivus</i> sp. n.
22	China, Yunnan, Weixi Lisu Autonomous County, Weideng Township, 27°05'N / 99°10'E	<i>Teledalpalpus linyejiei</i>
23	China, Yunnan, Dali Bay Autonomous Prefecture, Diancang Shan Mts, above Dali, 2500–2700 m, 25°41'N / 100°06'E	<i>Teledalpalpus daliensis</i> sp. n.
24	China, Yunnan, Yingjiang County, Xima env., ~2000 m, 24°43'N / 97°46'E	<i>Teledalpalpus</i> sp.
25	Vietnam, Hoang Lien Son Province, Sapa env., Fan Si Pan, 2400 m, 22°18–25'N / 103°49–54'E	<i>Teledalpalpus aranea</i>
26	Thailand, Doi Inthanon, 2500 m, 18°35'N / 98°29'E	<i>Parateledapus gibbus</i>

Figs 81–87. Species of Teledapini and Xylosteini, body part with a right wing.
 81 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 82 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n., holotype; 83 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 84 – *Teledapalpus hospes*; 85 – *Xylosteus spinolae* Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1838; 86 – *X. caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1936; 87 – *X. bartoni* Obenberger et Mařan, 1933. 81–82 – males; 83–87 – females.
 Рис. 81–87. Виды триб Teledapini и Xylosteini, часть тела с правым крылом.
 81 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 82 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n., голотип; 83 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 84 – *Teledapalpus hospes*; 85 – *Xylosteus spinolae* Frivaldszky von Frivald, 1838; 86 – *X. caucasicola* Plavilstshikov, 1936; 87 – *X. bartoni* Obenberger et Mařan, 1933. 81–82 – самцы; 83–87 – самки.

Figs 88–95. Species of Teledapini and Xylosteini, ventral body part (without head).
 88–89 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 90 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 91 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n., holotype; 92 – *Xylosteus spinolae*; 93 – *X. caucasicola*;
 94 – *X. kadleci* Miroshnikov, 2000, paratype; 95 – *X. bartoni*. 88, 90, 92–95 – females; 89, 91 – males.
 Рис. 88–95. Виды триб Teledapini и Xylosteini, нижняя часть тела (без головы).
 88–89 – *Teledapus dorcadioides*; 90 – *Teledapalpus zolotichini*; 91 – *Teledapalpus lobanovi* sp. n., голотип; 92 – *Xylosteus spinolae*; 93 – *X. caucasicola*;
 94 – *X. kadleci* Miroshnikov, 2000, паратип; 95 – *X. bartoni*. 88, 90, 92–95 – самки; 89, 91 – самцы.

Figs 96–102. Species of Xylosteini, ventral body part (without head) and elytra.
 96, 101 – *Xylosteus causicola*; 97, 99 – *X. bartoni*; 98, 102 – *Leptorhabdium causicum* (Kraatz, 1879); 100 – *X. kadleci*, paratype. 96–97, 99–101 – males; 98, 102 – females.

Рис. 96–102. Виды трибы Xylosteini, нижняя часть тела (без головы) и надкрылья.
 96, 101 – *Xylosteus causicola*; 97, 99 – *X. bartoni*; 98, 102 – *Leptorhabdium causicum* (Kraatz, 1879); 100 – *X. kadleci*, паратип. 96–97, 99–101 – самцы; 98, 102 – самки.

In addition, it should be noted that some genera previously placed in the Xylosteini, in particular *Capnolymma* Pascoe, 1858 (including *Acapnolymma* Gressitt et Rondon, 1970) [Gressitt, Rondon, 1970], are listed in the Rhagiini Kirby, 1837 in the aforementioned catalogues [Catalogue..., 2020; Chen et al., 2019]. However, I have already stressed the fact that these genera, most likely, should be placed in a separate new tribe [Miroshnikov, 2014]. By now, these ideas of mine have developed stronger. The systematic position of both genera, and the genus *Apiocephalus* Gahan, 1898, should be revised considering the above facts. This point of view is supported not only by some peculiar morphological features of adults of these genera ([Gressitt, Rondon, 1970; Ohbayashi, 1994; Miroshnikov, 2013]; unpublished data of the author), but also by the very peculiar traits of larvae of *Capnolymma* and *Apiocephalus* [Švácha, Lawrence, 2014].

Distribution. Holarctic and Oriental (Indochina) realms.

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